

Scalability on pre-exascale EuroHPC systems Deliverable D1.3

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Front figure: *Visualisation of a two-day forecast of the so called “Blue Marble” photograph, taken by the Apollo 17 crew in 1972, with a coupled ICON simulation a global horizontal resolution of 1.25 km (right), original NASA Blue Marble photo left. Credit: MPI-M, DKRZ, NVIDIA.*

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1 Abstract / publishable summary

The central objectives of Work Package 1 of ESiWACE2 is to develop and run coupled model simulations at a resolution as high as possible and with a throughput rate of at least one simulated year per day (1 SYPD) producing full model output. This throughput would be sufficient to use these simulations for operational weather predictions and potentially also to run the models for a couple of decades, to address scientific questions that are related to climate change. Four model configurations are considered: EC-Earth with OpenIFS coupled to NEMO, the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) coupled to NEMO, the ICON model with both atmosphere and ocean, the DYNAMICO model coupled to NEMO, covering both weather and climate configurations as well as well-established models and models that are currently under development. Furthermore, ocean-only simulations with the NEMO models are also pushed to very high spatial resolution ($1/36^\circ$; ~ 3 km).

According to the initial plan, the main aim of this deliverable was to perform scalability tests on the pre-exascale EuroHPC systems. However, this was impossible as these machines are only just becoming available. The deliverable is therefore focusing on the ongoing work to make the models more efficient and to enable the porting of the codes to heterogeneous hardware. As the European pre-exascale machines were not available, some tests of the models on other European HPC systems and some of the world's fastest supercomputers (Summit and Fugaku) are also documented. Furthermore, the work on the treatment of output from ensemble simulations using XIOS that was moved from Deliverable D1.1 is also documented here, showing the successful use of XIOS to generate ensemble model output straight from ensemble simulations.

2 Conclusion & Results

The deliverable is documenting the work on the production mode simulations that has continued as part of Work Package 1. The four model configurations are developing nicely and are performing well on the supercomputers of the consortium. Three of four models are close to, or have already met the throughput rate that was outlined in the proposal at the targeted or higher resolution, with no need to scale to the size of the pre-exascale machines.

However, the porting of the model configurations to heterogeneous hardware, and in particular GPUs, remains a challenging task for the modelling groups. This is even true when models that were running well on NVIDIA GPUs are now ported to AMD GPUs on LUMI-G. This is illustrating the importance of the work on Domain Specific Languages (DSLs) in Work Package 2.

It is also evident that the high throughput rates which can now be achieved for the high-resolution model configurations as a result of the work of this work package, will be sufficient to produce an overwhelming amount of data that cannot possibly be stored at full resolution and high temporal frequency. This makes tools such as the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) of Work Package 4 as well as ESiWACE's support to facilitate access to output of the DYAMOND model intercomparison essential.

While the models could not yet be ported to the pre-exascale machines and tested at pre-exascale due to the delay of the access to the machines, the model configurations are generally in good shape to hit the ground running, when the machines are becoming available. Furthermore, the model configurations that were developed in this work package are now already taken up by large EU research and infrastructure projects, that will exploit the model configurations of this deliverable for scientific studies – for example in nextGEMS, EERIE or WarmWorld – and future operational simulations of weather and climate – for example in the Destination Earth (DestinE) project.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	X
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	X

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Model developments

This section provides an overview how the development of the four coupled models for production mode simulations and the high-resolution configuration of NEMO has progressed during the last year.

Unfortunately, the access to the pre-exascale EuroHPC systems has been delayed. Marenostrum5 is not running yet, Leonardo and LUMI-G have joined the top 500 list of supercomputers in November 2022. There was some limited access to LUMI-G to the ICON and IFS development teams. However, the available time was not sufficient to port the complex models to run efficiently and at scale on the AMD GPUs and developments were slowed down by system down-times. There was so far no access available to Leonardo for the production mode simulations of ESIWACE. Therefore, there are no scalability plots on the pre-exascale supercomputers of EuroHPC that can be reported in this deliverable and the extrapolation to the exa-scale remains a task for future work when GPU-based pre-exascale machines become available. However, the developments to improve and optimise the production mode simulations continued and the consortium could get access to large supercomputing systems – such as Levante, Vega or the new ECMWF supercomputer – that still allowed to perform meaningful tests regarding scalability and throughput.

The following sections will summarise the progress and developments for each of the modelling systems since the last deliverable of Work Package 1, *Deliverable D1.1: Simulations of global high-resolution climate and weather models in production mode* (Serradell et al., 2021).

4.1.1 ECMWF's model IFS

The Integrated Forecast System (IFS) is a global coupled numerical weather prediction model developed by ECMWF. A comprehensive description of the IFS can be found in deliverable D1.1, but here we briefly summarise it. The IFS consists of separate model components for each part of the Earth system. The most predominant in terms of code size and complexity, and usually computational cost, is the atmospheric component. This is also often referred to simply as “the IFS”. The IFS atmosphere consists of a dynamical core and a suite of physical parametrisation schemes. The dynamical core uses a semi-implicit semi-Lagrangian time-stepping scheme performed across two computational grids: one in the space of spherical harmonics (spectral space) and an octahedral discretisation of the sphere (grid point space). Calculations occur either in spectral space or grid point space depending on where they can be represented most efficiently, and meteorological fields are transformed back and forth between these two spaces by a spectral transform module, now provided by the open-source library ecTrans. ecTrans supports either CPUs or GPUs. In addition to the dynamical core, the model contains a suite of physical parametrisation schemes for representing phenomena that occur below the scale of the octahedral grid or otherwise aren't represented by the basic fluid equations. This includes long-wave and short-wave radiation, cloud microphysics, convection, and gravity-wave induced drag. Global fields are decomposed by a partitioning algorithm and distributed among potentially many thousands of compute tasks, with MPI providing communication between tasks. Within compute tasks, OpenMP provides an additional level of parallelism.

Separately, the ocean component is handled by the NEMO model, which features prominently in many of the modelling systems of Work Package 1 and a more detailed description of NEMO can be found in subsection 4.1.5. The IFS atmosphere is coupled to a fork of NEMO, which as of Deliverable D1.1 was based on version 3.4. Since then this has been upgraded to a version based on NEMO 4.0. In addition, support for OpenMP parallelism and single-precision arithmetic has been added by ECMWF, and it is this version which we use for the results below. On top of the ocean, the IFS includes a model for the ocean surface waves known as WAM.

As well as the internal high-performance computer system at ECMWF, based on the Atos Bullsequana XH2000, the IFS has been ported, tested, and benchmarked on a variety of computing platforms around the world. Notable recent examples include Summit at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory in the USA, Fugaku at the RIKEN Centre for Computational Science in Japan, JUWELS at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre in Germany, and now the pre-exascale EuroHPC system LUMI in Finland. Due to the limited access the work on the European pre-exascale systems has been limited. However, intensive work is now ongoing to allow very high-resolution integrations of the IFS on the GPU partition of LUMI, LUMI-G, with significant parts of the model offloaded to GPUs. The porting work that has been started as part of ESiWACE with a focus of those IFS model components that are part of the HPCW dwarfs and in particular the spectral transform library, will be continued by the DestinE project¹ once the current phase of ESiWACE has finished, so the efforts will be sustained in the future. However, the work is still in the testing stage, and we are therefore not yet able to present scalability results on the pre-exascale machines in this deliverable. The second machine to become available, is Leonardo. The hardware of Leonardo is close to JUWELS-Booster, and therefore we do not expect significant technical hurdles in achieving good scalability of the IFS there. However, the machine is not yet open for use to us. We hope to have a significant allocation through Leonardo's early-access program in the beginning of 2023. On the whole, we are not able to present comprehensive results of the IFS's scalability on any pre-exascale EuroHPC machines. Nevertheless, we can present results from the other machines mentioned that will still help to draw useful conclusions relevant to the ESiWACE goals, and to prepare for the use of the machines once they become available.

¹The Destination Earth (DestinE) project is funded by the EC's Horizon Europe programme. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/destination-earth-destine>

Figure 1: Weak scalability test of the IFS on Summit, with spectral transforms offloaded to GPUs. “Coupled” results employed the full atmosphere-ocean-wave system. For “uncoupled” the ocean component was excluded.

IFS scalability on Summit

Summit, based at the Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (OLCF), was the highest ranking supercomputer in the world from November 2018 to June 2020. The system is comprised of around 4,600 compute nodes, each consisting of two POWER9 IBM CPUs and six Nvidia V100 GPUs. The POWER9 CPUs, operating at 3.07 GHz, have 22 “SIMD Multi-Cores” each, and each core supports up to four threads through Simultaneous Multi-Threading technology. In terms of cache and memory, each core has its own L1d and L1i caches of 32 kB each, each pair of cores share 512 kB of L2 cache and 10 MB of L3 cache, and the two CPUs share 512 GB of DDR4 memory. On the other hand the V100 GPUs have 16 GB of High Bandwidth Memory, HBM2, each. The GPUs are connected to their host CPUs and each other by NVLink. The system employs a dual-rail EDR InfiniBand network to connect the compute nodes. All-in-all, Summit delivers a peak performance of about 200 petaFLOPS. Through a series of large allocations provided by the Department of Energy’s INCITE program, ECMWF has been granted access to Summit for a number of years. In this time, the IFS model has undergone substantial optimisation to make best use of the GPUs of Summit, such that it is now possible to run simulations even up to 1.5 km resolution with the spectral transform calculations entirely offloaded to the V100s. The latest round of simulations carried out for INCITE even included a high-resolution ocean component, with NEMO running on an eORCA12 grid (extended ORCA grid with $1/12^\circ$ resolution). Here we discuss the performance of the IFS on Summit as it was used for these simulations.

Figure 1 summarises the performance of the coupled IFS system on Summit in a weak-scaling context. We carried out this test for the atmosphere-only configuration (“uncoupled”) and also with a coupled dynamic $1/12^\circ$ ocean model (“coupled”). In both cases model output was disabled to not pollute throughput estimates with IO time that depends on adjustable resources. In this test, as the atmospheric horizontal resolution is scaled up, from TCO639 (around 16 km) to TCO7999 (1.5 km), the allocation of compute nodes was increased roughly in proportion to the increase in computational work. The number of vertical levels in the atmosphere is held at 137. Perfect scalability would be indicated by a flat line of performance in terms of simulated-years-per-day. In reality, the line deviates from this ideal due to imperfect scaling of certain model components, notably the communication-heavy spectral transform (which performs several all-to-all communications every time step). Nevertheless, the scaling of the model is decent and we are able to make effective use of even almost 6,000 GPUs on Summit. Note that the unusual increase in throughput for the coupled case is likely a

consequence of keeping a fixed ocean resolution for all atmospheric resolutions. This is therefore not strictly speaking a weak-scaling test. We have much less flexibility for varying the ocean resolution, compared with the atmospheric resolution.

Going forward we will consider negotiating access to other American exascale systems, such as Frontier, through INCITE. These very large systems are useful for scalability studies. Unfortunately, none of the current makeup of large American supercomputers make use of Nvidia GPUs. Frontier, for example, is very similar to LUMI with the bulk of its compute provided by AMD GPUs. This means we cannot simply carry over our version of the IFS from Summit to Frontier. On this machine we would encounter much the same issues of portability that we currently encounter on LUMI. Therefore we have decided not to pursue further allocations on American systems until we can demonstrate reliable and efficient use of the non-Nvidia GPUs these systems rely on.

IFS scalability on Fugaku

Fugaku, based at the RIKEN Centre for Computational Science (R-CCS), was the highest ranking supercomputer in the world from June 2020 until June 2022. Fugaku is unusual among top-ranking supercomputers in being entirely homogeneous both within nodes and across the system, consisting of 158,976 identical compute nodes. Unlike other machines, it does not rely on any GPU technology, with each compute node instead consisting of a single Fujitsu A64FX CPU. However, the A64FX is not an ordinary CPU. It uses the ARM Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) — its CPU is enhanced and inherited superior features from the SPARC64 (which underpinned its predecessor, the K Computer) for its core pipeline. Each A64FX CPU features 48 compute cores divided among 4 “Core Memory Groups” (CMGs), which are essentially different NUMA regions. The chip is available with clock speeds of 1.8, 2.0, and 2.2 GHz, though Fugaku’s CPUs operate at 2.0 GHz in normal operation (they can be boosted to 2.2 GHz). Each core has about 64 kB of both L1d and L1i cache and each CMG has about 8 MB of shared L2 cache. Unusually, there is no L3 cache nor any traditional DDR memory on the compute nodes of Fugaku. Instead the function of both is served by around 34 GB of HBM2 memory (the same technology found in the V100 GPUs of Summit) per node. The A64FX also has an unusually wide vector register size of 512-bit. The many, many compute nodes of Fugaku are connected with a “Tofu Interconnect D” system. ECMWF and R-CCS signed a two-year Memorandum of Understanding in late 2020 for the purposes of evaluating the performance of weather and climate codes on Fugaku, with a particular focus on the potential benefits for half-precision (16-bit) calculations. In supporting the latter natively in hardware, the A64FX is unique among CPUs. Thanks to this collaboration, we were able to perform benchmarks of the IFS on this extreme-scale machine.

Figure 2 shows the weak-scalability performance of the IFS on Fugaku. Here the IFS is integrated for 24 hours without any output in atmosphere-only mode (i.e., not coupled to a dynamic ocean model) across a variety of horizontal atmospheric resolutions. The number of vertical levels is fixed at 137. As with the Summit experiments, we aimed to keep the amount of computational work per compute node roughly constant as we scale up the horizontal resolution. The IFS shows good scalability up to the current operational high-resolution forecast resolution of TCO1279 (about 9 km). In this regard, we can consider Fugaku to be a very fast machine, though we would discourage direct comparison with the results from Summit in Figure 1 due to the very different architectures of these two machines. Unfortunately, we were not able to obtain good performance from Fugaku at the next highest resolution that we considered, TCO2559 (about 4 km). Here we suffered from the severe memory limitations of the A64FX CPU, which has only about 28 GB of usable high-bandwidth HBM2 memory. Due to the much increased per-node memory demands of this TCO2559 configuration, we had no choice but to reduce the number of MPI ranks allocated to each compute node (assigning the freed cores to more OpenMP threads) in order to keep within this limited memory capacity. As a consequence, we suffered a substantial performance drop at this resolution of about a factor two. In addition, we were not able to run simulations at any higher resolutions even after reducing the number of MPI ranks per node to just one. It is possible that further work could bring down the memory footprint of the IFS to enable a more efficient allocation of MPI ranks. Since we concluded work on Fugaku, for example, we have

Figure 2: Weak scalability test of the IFS on Fugaku,

discovered enormous benefits in terms of a reduction in memory demands from using different decompositions of fields in spectral space. However at the time we did not have the human resources to carry out this work on Fugaku. Nevertheless our experiences on Fugaku give us hope for the continued relevance of CPU technology, with new innovations brought from the ARM instruction set. The problems of limited memory on Fugaku are not fundamental, but indicate that the hardware configuration is not optimal for the requirements of IFS. The European HPC community should keep a close eye on future developments in this realm, particularly relating to the European Processor Initiative which aims to deliver a European ARM-based CPU ecosystem by the end of the decade.

Single-precision NEMO in coupled IFS integrations

As mentioned above, ECMWF has added support for single-precision arithmetic to the ocean model NEMO, building on earlier work by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre. The philosophy regarding single precision in the ocean is the same as for the atmosphere (which has been in operational use since May 2021): use single precision for as many variables as possible, and where necessary to avoid instability or otherwise deleterious results, promote variables back to double precision. In fact there are hardly any cases where this re-promotion to double precision was necessary. The forecast scores obtained when using single precision in NEMO are of course not the same for the reference case, double precision. Nevertheless, we are satisfied that there will be no impact on the lead times that are relevant to ECMWF, even up to the seasonal timescale. ECMWF plans to implement single-precision ocean integrations in 2024 as part of cycle upgrade 49r1.

With this development we are able to run a fully single-precision coupled forecast for the first time, and we have been performing extensive benchmarks of this system on the new Atos high-performance computer at ECMWF. The computational gains from using single precision in NEMO vary dramatically based on the context in which the simulations occur. For ocean-only integrations (forced by reanalysis, for example), there is a consistent acceleration of about $1.8\times$ across all ocean resolution configurations. We are also able to achieve such an acceleration for coupled cases with a low resolution atmosphere, such as in the seasonal forecasting system. Figure 4a gives the performance in simulated-days-per-day (SDPD) of our coupled system in this configuration, with a TCO319 resolution atmosphere and a $1/4^\circ$ ocean. When we use single precision in the ocean, the ocean itself is accelerated by $1.8\times$ and, since the ocean comprises a significant fraction of the total cost of the system in this case, the overall coupled model is accelerated by about $1.27\times$. For high-resolution cases, such as in Figure 4b with a TCO2559 atmosphere and a $1/12^\circ$ ocean, the gains are not so great. Here

Figure 3: Benchmarks of the IFS on the ECMWF Atos high-performance computer with a double- and single-precision ocean component. We used 8 compute nodes for case (a) and 400 for case (b).

the ocean itself is only accelerated by $1.27\times$ and the overall coupled system is only accelerated by about $1.01\times$, which is not statistically significant. The lack of overall performance improvement from using single precision in NEMO is not surprising: even with a $1/12^\circ$ grid, the cost of the ocean is very small compared with the TCO2559 atmosphere. The question of why the performance gains for the ocean itself are so limited is an outstanding problem. However, as we achieved a much better acceleration of $1/12^\circ$ simulations in an ocean-only context. Furthermore, performance improvements of the ocean model are still essential as a $1/12^\circ$ grid ocean model is causing roughly 50% of the runtime in simulations that are coupling to a TCO1279 atmosphere – the resolution which is currently used for operational weather predictions at ECMWF.

IFS on LUMI

To run IFS on Lumi is non-trivial as the model components need to be able to run on AMD GPUs. The process is started via the porting of the ectrans library to the new hardware. The easiest option to port the existing GPU version of ectrans to AMD GPUs was to continue using OpenACC and to "hipify" the CUDA functions which call the batched matrix multiplication inside the Legendre transform and the FFT for the Fourier transform. The only compiler compatible with AMD GPUs with sufficient support for OpenACC is the Cray compiler which is only available on supercomputers built by HPE (Cray). The currently fastest supercomputer in Europe LUMI is an HPE machine. The main issue of this work was that the late access to LUMI and that the GPUs of LUMI were often not available for many weeks due to HPE preventing access for benchmarking purposes and we could not get access to any other supercomputer with AMD GPUs and recent Cray software stack. The only alternative during those times without access to LUMI's GPUs was to use AMD GPUs on the AMD cloud platform in Munich. This machine provides an even newer version of the ROCm software package from AMD but does not provide any Cray compiler and therefore no OpenACC support.

In July 2022 we did manage to create a first OpenMP offloading version of ectrans and successfully ran a spectral transform on the NVIDIA GPUs of the supercomputer Summit. The AMD Fortran compiler supports OpenMP offloading but it does not yet support all the features of Fortran which we need to compile the entire ectrans library. For this reason we started with standalone batched matrix multiplication and FFT codes extracted from ectrans. These work now correctly with all available combinations of compilers and programming models: Cray+OpenACC, Cray+OpenMP and AMD+OpenMP. For the CUDA we first gained some experience by porting the matrix multiplication to HIP by hand. For the FFT we used the hipify perl

script provided by the ROCm software package from AMD. Using hipblas and hipfft allows us to stay relatively close to the previous code developed for NVIDIA GPUs. Hipfft uses on AMD GPUs rocfft which can also be used directly. Rocfft should provide more features and more control over the computation. In our simple standalone codes we did not find any situation where the features of hipfft were not sufficient for ectrans but we might explore using rocfft directly in the future.

There were some changes necessary to make the matrix multiplication and FFT work with the Cray and AMD compilers. The main changes are (in the order in which we worked on them):

1. As safety check we introduced for the NVIDIA compiler DEFAULT(NONE) in many of the OpenACC directives. The NVIDIA compiler still did not require all variable to be listed in a PRESENT clause while the Cray compiler (correctly) requires all variables to be listed in either COPY or PRESENT clauses. We added corresponding PRESENT clauses to our OpenACC directives.
2. According to the OpenACC specification the device type when calling `acc_set_device_num` needs to be an integer of kind `acc_device_kind`. The Cray compiler reqgmd-15-379-2022uires this kind while the NVIDIA compiler worked fine with the default integer kind. We are now using `acc_device_kind` which works with the NVIDIA and Cray compiler.
3. We have not been able to use shared libraries on LUMI. The support ticket for this is still open. We have not yet found a way to create a small reproducer for this issue. For now we compile all libraries as static libraries.
4. Cmake did not correctly use HIP compile flags when using `HIP_SOURCE_PROPERTY_FORMAT`. For now we specify the compile flags manually.
5. The kind type parameters of the integer arguments when calling our CUDA functions via iso-c-binding were wrong. Cray and AMD compilers did not work without fixing these.

The hope is to perform first scalability tests once ectrans can run efficiently on LUMI.

Conclusion

As documented in the previous deliverable D1.1, our production mode simulations are running successfully with a higher (4 km atmosphere and 25 km ocean) resolution than promised in the proposal and with more model output (the operational instead of the research setting) at 0.95 SYPD on ECMWF's ATOS supercomputer. The main goal has therefore been achieved. While we could not run the model on the pre-exascale EuroHPC machines, we were able to scale the model to large fractions of three of the fastest supercomputers available – Summit, Juwels Booster and Fugaku. The configuration of the IFS production mode simulations is used successfully in large EU projects such as nextGEMS² and DestinE and is therefore already driving research applications and is in preparation for operational use.

However, the porting to new hardware of modern supercomputers remains difficult. Difficulties to run model code on AMD GPUs on LUMI, that was used successfully on NVIDIA GPUs before, testifies that the porting to future machines will continue to be a challenge. However, WP2 of ESiWACE2 helped to enhance domain specific languages for weather and climate modelling and IFS will soon be able to fully exploit the use of Loki for physical parametrisation schemes and GT4Py for the IFS-FVM dynamical core, which will make the use of future EuroHPC machines much easier. Furthermore, the collaboration with HPC experts, including those in WP3 from NLeSC and Atos, is very fruitful to solve existing bottlenecks and challenges.

4.1.2 The EC-EARTH model

EC-Earth is a state-of-the-art Earth System Model, which is developed by the EC-Earth consortium by complementing, integrating and coupling independent components for the simulation of the physical domains of the

²The nextGEMS project is funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme. <https://nextgems-h2020.eu>

Earth system. EC-Earth 4, the most recent generation of the model, builds, for its base GCM configuration, on the most recent versions of OpenIFS, NEMO, OASIS and XIOS.

In order to adapt EC-Earth 4 to current EuroHPC systems and their HPC architecture, two approaches are pursued: native porting to the machines of interest, and using containerisation in order to provide portable installations that can be easily installed on different machines. The latter approach was implemented during the ESiWACE2 *Container Hackathon for Modellers*³, where an early EC-Earth 4 was containerised and tested (see D2.9 (Sawyer et al., 2023) for details). This proof-of-concept implementation with Docker⁴ for the container development and the Saurus⁵ engine for deployment provided valuable knowledge and practical experience for future installations of EC-Earth 4 with containers.

The next section describes in further detail an attempt to follow the first of the two approaches to make EuroHPC systems accessible for EC-Earth 4, namely the native porting of the model to one of the early systems that were available through EuroHPC.

Porting EC-Earth 4 to the EuroHPC Vega system

SMHI has led an effort to port and test EC-Earth 4 to EuroHPC machines, targeting the same computer architecture that is used on pre-exascale machines, such as LUMI. A PRACE type B preparatory access was granted for that purpose under the proposal *EC-Earth 4: Data Intensive Computing* (PRACE proposal no. 2010PA5857) for the Vega HPC system at the Institute of Information Science (IZUM), Maribor, Slovenia. This project has addressed two important bottlenecks for the computational performance of EC-Earth 4:

- Improve performance of OpenIFS for high-resolution grids
- Improve performance for high-frequency output

The computational cost for the atmospheric component (OpenIFS) is a limiting factor for EC-Earth experiments at high resolution, a bottleneck that could be mitigated by using the hybrid MPI-OpenMP parallelization that is implemented in OpenIFS. However, this has never been implemented in previous EC-Earth versions, which used older versions of the atmosphere model, due to difficulties originating from the multi-executable, coupled architecture of the model. Earlier tests, some of them performed within ESiWACE activities, had shown that it is possible to run OpenIFS in hybrid parallelization mode, thereby improving the performance of the overall model.

The project was also supposed to address the effect of high-frequency output from OpenIFS. EC-Earth 4 implements a new I/O subsystem for the atmosphere, the fully parallel (in contrast to previous EC-Earth versions) XIOS software. While the output system has already been tested for functionality, the computational cost of high-frequency (sub-daily) output has not been thoroughly analyzed and XIOS settings have not been optimized. The latter point is crucial to achieve good performance, since XIOS offers a variety of options to control the parallelization and workflow of the I/O subsystem.

Vega was the first of a number of HPC systems with similar architecture (many-core AMD Epyc nodes and using SLURM) that was available to us. Unfortunately, we could never overcome the issues with launching the EC-Earth 4 model reliably in a practical configuration. In the process of solving the issues described above, many lessons were learned that proved useful for deploying the model on similar systems. Unfortunately, our inability to launch heterogeneous multi-executable jobs with SLURM on Vega finally prevented us from doing any actual scalability testing or running practical climate experiments.

In particular, the following issues were encountered and reported during the project:

- OpenMPI errors (SLING #2300333)
 - find correct modules, launchers and options

³Details and documentation at <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/container-hackathon-for-modellers>

⁴See [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Docker_(software)) and <https://www.docker.com/>

⁵Sarus - An OCI-compatible container engine for HPC, see <https://sarus.readthedocs.io>

- configure UCX correctly
- resolved by correct configuration, with good help of support
- Unreliable launch configuration (SLING #2300365)
 - configuration from previous issue (#2300333) not working reliably
 - applications stops with segfaults in MPI libs and UCX errors
 - support suggests RDMA error
 - issue never resolved, superseded by next issue
- SLURM issues (SLING #2300416)
 - not able to launch hybrid MPI/OpenMP multi-executable configuration
 - configuration working on other systems, but not Vega
 - allocation of nodes/tasks-per-node working with salloc+srunch, but not with sbatch+srunch
 - support concludes a bug in the SLURM version on Vega, promises SLURM update
 - issue closed, not resolved (10/2021)

During the final months of the Vega allocation, we spent a lot of time on other systems where the model could be successfully launched, thus limiting the effort on further investigations on Vega.

We anticipated the placing and binding of MPI-process and OpenMP threads to the computational resources (nodes, cores, memory) to be crucial for the performance of the coupled mode. Early tests with non-optimal binding and poor performance seemed to confirm this presumption.

As a result, two different methods were implemented to interface with the SLURM-MPI process/thread binding system: one based on the taskset tool and another based on SLURM heterogeneous jobs. However, none of the methods could reliably be employed with EC-Earth4 on Vega. The main difficulty seems to be the multi-executable architecture of the code, which added another layer of complexity and lacked the full support of the SLURM system, at least at the time of the Vega preparatory access.

As mentioned above, the Vega system is one of the earlier machines of a common architecture that has become available in Europe and elsewhere. Even other EuroHPC systems (e.g. LUMI-C) are based on the AMD-Epyc many-core architecture and we consider porting EC-Earth4 to this kind of machine as an important task. It is unfortunate that we could never overcome all difficulties of launching the model reliably in a production-like configuration. The more so because we otherwise found the environment on the Vega system appropriate and, not the least, the support by IZUM very helpful and responsive.

We did see progress over the time of the project, but unfortunately some of the proposed solutions were out of our control (such as vendor upgrades of software) and the one year project proved too short to get everything into place. We finally did manage to develop a reliable launching mechanism on other machines, but too late to conclude with any actual scaling tests on the Vega EuroHPC system.

Porting EC-Earth 4 to the LUMI system

Since November 2022, BSC led the effort to port and test EC-Earth4 to LUMI. The work was performed in two consecutive attempts, using different compiling environments. In the first attempt, the target was to run using the Cray Programming Environment. Due to significant technical difficulties preventing the completion of the tests and the small time window in which LUMI was completely available, we decided to focus on using the more compatible GNU compiling environment.

In both cases, work involved deploying the EC-Earth4 source code in LUMI, choosing the appropriate available modules, deploying dependencies not available as modules, creating a new build configuration file for the particular programming environment, compiling the different components (fixing issues arisen during compilation), adapting the running scripts, and executing the tests.

Figure 4: EC-Earth 4 Tco639-ORCA12 scaling on MareNostrum4 (Intel) and LUMI-C (GNU)

A few issues had to be addressed to compile EC-Earth 4 in the Cray Environment, including removing a few line comments in OASIS and adapting OpenIFS to include the correct Cray FFT library filename. However, some XIOS functions not fulfilling the standard and only leading to warnings during the compilation prevented EC-Earth 4 from running at all with the Cray environment. A few dozen of functions needed a fix in their return value. After these corrective measures, the model could start initializing, but an error that occurred in the Rearranger module of the MCT library prevented the model from initializing completely. This problem was a symptom of an issue in the communications layer and was very difficult to debug.

In the case of GNU, the compilation was much more straightforward, and completing this process was only a question of choosing the appropriate compilation flags.

We could execute the test Tco95-ORCA1 configuration and deploy the final Tco639-ORCA12 VHR demonstrator. The scaling did not have model output enabled since enabling it in very-high resolution led to memory and network issues. We could scale the Tco639-ORCA12 configuration up to 180 LUMI-C nodes, where throughput peaks at 2.9 SYPD. This is three times the proposed mark of 1 SYPD and 30% more than what we achieved in MareNostrum4. In LUMI, core-to-core performance is similar to MareNostrum4 on low core counts. These numbers should improve with Cray compilers. On the higher core counts, scalability is superior on LUMI.

When scaling the model on more than 30 nodes, we experienced communication issues along the lines of the ones reported in the Vega subchapter. For example, some overflow errors were suggesting to increase the `FI_CXI_DEFAULT_CQ_SIZE` value, which was not a definite solution, as the model was rather hung instead of crashing. However, securing the message matching with `FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MODE="hybrid"` seemed to be a good compromise to scale the model far from 40 nodes. From 100 nodes onwards, behavior was more erratic, with internal MPI errors (connection reset, etc) of different kinds in many of the simulations.

Additional work done for efficient runs on CPU systems as LUMI-C or MN4

Although there is future work to exploit parallelism on GPUs for the components of EC-Earth as IFS or NEMO, BSC worked in different aspects to ensure that the actual version of the model could exploit in the most efficient way the CPU partions, speeding up the model as fast as we could. The next aspects were done to make this possible.

Load balance of EC-Earth 4

We can call coupling cost as the time spent for a coupled earth system model to exchange fields between the different components included, as fields exchanged between the ocean and the atmospheric part (free surface, as a real example). Load balance of a coupled model means that the time needed to exchange those fields is minimum because the time execution of the different components is very similar.

We have seen that the load balance of EC-Earth significantly impacts its performance, and the existing tool for evaluating the coupling impact, included in the OASIS-MCT code (LUCIA) did not provide enough information to minimize the coupling cost. In December 2021, we reached an agreement with the OASIS developers and collaborated on the development of a new load balancing analysis tool, which has been incorporated into OASIS-MCT-5.0. Consequently, in EC-Earth 4, we are being able to use this tool to improve the load balance. Additionally, we have new workflow that automatically determine the optimal resource setup for any given EC-Earth configuration, taking into consideration the time-to-solution, energy-to-solution and maximum parallelization requirements. With the combination of a new tool to get the performance metrics related to the coupling, and a new automatic methodology to achieve the best load balanced configuration, we will ensure that EC-Earth4 experiments will run with the best number of processes for each component in CPU partitions.

XIOS integration

One of the main bottlenecks of EC-Earth 3 is in the writing of IFS model output. This particular IFS version uses a sequential I/O scheme which gathers all data and writes via the single master process. However, this approach is not scalable for higher resolution configurations where many MPI processes are used and a large amount of data is written. In order to solve this bottleneck, we integrated XIOS into OpenIFS as described by Yepes-Arbós et al. (2022). The initial work was performed in IFS CY43R3 and later ported to OpenIFS.

We created an IFS-XIOS interface to minimise the code changes in IFS so that it can be easily ported to future versions of IFS/OpenIFS. This integration makes use of FullPos as all the post-processing features of this package are not available in XIOS. This include different kind of vertical interpolations: pressure levels, theta (potential temperature) levels and potential vorticity (PV) levels. Another important aspect is regarding the spectral fields. XIOS only support gridded data, so the integration also transforms spectral fields to their grid-point representation before sending them from IFS to XIOS.

The integration was thoroughly tested, not only to check the correctness, but also the performance efficiency. According to the tests, the use of XIOS proves an improvement in the I/O efficiency of IFS/OpenIFS. While this was a high-impact bottleneck in EC-Earth 3, with the proper XIOS setup this is not an issue in EC-Earth 4.

Mixed-precision

A mixed precision version of NEMO was created starting from the version 4.2. This will be available in NEMO starting from the official release 4.2.1. This version was implemented using an automatic approach developed at BSC Tintó Prims et al. (2019), based on a library developed at ECMWF Dawson and Düben (2017) in 2016. The workflow implements a binary tree search among the NEMO real precision variables, highlighting the ones that cannot be demoted to single precision. It can be thought as a source to source tool, since at the end of the process produces a valide non-preprocessed Fortran90 code. The mixed-precision version has been tested for climate simulation with neutral impact on result up to 30 years at low resolution, with an improvement in performance of around 30%. The specific EC-Earth 4 version discussed in this deliverable is not making use of this version, since is using NEMO4.0. We are anyway positive about the fact that this development will be used in future release of EC-Earth 4 with clear benefits on its computational performance.

Conclusion

As documented in the previous deliverable D1.1, we fulfilled the goal of reaching 1 SYPD with model output, not only with a climatic production configuration but also with a large output that increased the stress in

the I/O subsystem. Moreover, we got very close to 2 SYPD with the production configuration in a Petascale machine as MareNostrum 4. This improvement is attributed to different factors, being the most important the newer model components, the new octahedral grid used in OpenIFS, and, importantly, the work carried on in this project to integrate OpenIFS with the asynchronous I/O server already used by NEMO.

Porting to new hardware of Petascale and Pre-exascale EuroHPC machines was difficult. Nevertheless, we succeeded in scaling the new model and configuration in the LUMI Pre-exascale machine, peaking at almost 3 SYPD and achieving a throughput three times higher as proposed (and six times higher than we could achieve in EC-Earth3). From this point, the challenge is to use the proprietary compilers and run some components in the accelerated partitions of LUMI or other Pre-exascale machines, such as MareNostrum5.

Although the new EC-Earth 4 has been deployed in CPU partitions as LUMI-C and MN4, we have explained the different approaches that the model can take advantage to speed up the execution and obtain a reasonable SYPD without accelerators. This will not only ensure that EC-Earth will be used in the new machines while a GPU porting is done and proved as efficient, but also maintaining a portable and general purpose implementation which can be used by a high range of users around Europe.

4.1.3 The ICON model

The ICON coupled model framework for weather and climate applications is based on a hybrid method with finite differences and finite volume approaches. It is discretized on an icosahedron-based triangular grid using an Arakawa C-grid approach. ICON's components are ICON-A, a non-hydrostatic atmosphere model based on developments at Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) and Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), and ICON-O, an ocean model, developed at MPI-M, using the same grid and discretized with a mimetic scheme. While ICON-A contains the land and surface model JSBACH and links to the chemistry model ICON-ART, ICON-O includes a sea ice model, which is an adaptation of a sea ice model developed at the Alfred-Wegener-Institute (AWI). A comprehensive description of ICON can be found in deliverable D1.1 as well as in (Hohenegger et al., 2022).

Beside DWD, MPI-M and DKRZ, many more partners are involved in the development of ICON (ICO). These partners are involved in many EU and nationally funded projects also aiming to improve ICON's scientific results as well as its usability, scalability and portability for the climate and weather community. At the moment, the most important projects in the scope of ICON developments are:

- ESiWACE2: This project attempts to boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre- and exascale platforms. Here, ICON is one of 4 flagship models which are aiming to forecast 1 SYPD in a production-mode simulation on a pre-exascale system with realistic output and at the highest resolution possible.
- nextGEMS: The models IFS and ICON will be developed to the next generation of earth-system models, where 30 years of global storm-resolving simulations become possible with a performance making climate simulations of longer time scales feasible again.
- WarmWorld⁶: In this project, ICON is rewritten and refactored to enable an improved usage of heterogeneous computing architectures, efficient use of pre-exascale machines and better connections of observation and simulation data.
- DestinE: Its participants aim to develop a global scale, highly accurate "digital twin" of the Earth's climate to monitor and predict the interaction between natural phenomena and human activities. ICON is one of two models here, and will be available in a quasi-operational fashion after the project.

⁶The WarmWorld project is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). <https://warmworld.de>

- CLICCS⁷: This Hamburg university centred project explores climate change with broad expertise. An essential part of CLICCS is climate modelling in order to exploit advances in HPC technologies. One of its goals is to enable ICON-O to run on GPUs.
- EXCLAIM⁸: The OpenETH project EXCLAIM aims at developing an ICON-model-framework based infrastructure that is capable of running kilometre-scale climate simulations at both regional and global scales for extreme scale computing and data platforms. Cloud-resolving weather and climate modelling are on the plate of to dos. The project has the ambition to provide this platform as a foundation for weather and climate modelling for the decades to come.

as well as the recently started projects EERIE⁹ and two SACLEXA projects¹⁰: IFCES2 and ExaOcean.

In the following we will describe the main developments in ICON, which are needed to run coupled simulations with realistic model output at highest resolution possible on a pre-exascale computer. These developments were mainly done within the projects: QUBICC¹¹, CLICCS, MONSOON-2.0¹², WarmWorld and ESiWACE2. Afterwards, results for the scalability of ICON running the ESiWACE2 target configuration (coupled simulation with a horizontal resolution of R2B9 and output) on the super computers Levante, Juwels Booster and LUMI will be shown and problems encountered on these systems will be described.

Porting ICON to GPUs

In the early 2000s, ICON was developed for use on either cache based or vectorizing CPUs. With the build-up of the hybrid PizDaint compute system at the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS), one of the most powerful supercomputers in that time, porting ICON to GPUs became a topic of interest. As part of the QUBICCproject, main parts of ICON-A were ported to GPUs mainly by using OpenACC directives. Although the project aimed to run it's experiments on PitzDaint and on the GPU partition Booster of the JUWELS system at Jülich Supercomputing Centre (FZJ), the use of directives enables the model to run the same code on GPUs as well as on CPUs. A detailed description of the experiment, the porting and its challenges as well as scientific results and scaling of the simulation on three different compute systems is given in by Giorgetta et.al., 2022. The main challenges encountered during porting to GPUs are shortly described in the following:

- data transfer between GPU and CPU:
On current supercomputer architectures, GPU and CPU have separate memories, and the transfer of data between the two goes via a slow connection compared to the direct access of the local memory of each device. To limit this data transfer, it was decided to port all computations occurring during the time loop to GPUs. In addition structured data regions had been employed. The data transfer was implemented by using MPI.
- data layout:
ICON-A operates on three-dimensional domains: the horizontal is split up into `nblocks` blocks of arbitrary size `npxoma` in order to offer flexibility for a variety of processors. The `nlev` vertical levels

⁷The Cluster of Excellence *Climate, Climatic Change, and Society* (CLICCS) is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). <https://www.cliccs.uni-hamburg.de>

⁸The project *EXtreme scale Computing and data platform for cLoud-resolving weAther and cllmate Modeling* (EXCLAIM) is funded by the ETH Zurich. <https://exclaim.ethz.ch>

⁹The *European Eddy-Rlch Earth system models* (EERIE) project is funded by the EU's Horizon Europe programme. <https://eerie-project.eu>

¹⁰SCALEXA is a funding call from the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). For more information on the projects started in Dec 2022, see <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc/news/news-items/news-flashes/2022/scalexa-projects>.

¹¹QUBICC, which stands for *Quasi-Biennial Oscillation in a Changing Climate (QUBICC)* and is a project of the ROMIC-II programme, founded by the BMBF.

¹²The BMBF-funded project MONSOON-2.0 was a cooperation of the German partners: Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, DKRZ and the German Aerospace Center (DLR), with the China Meteorological Administration and the National Supercomputing Center in Wuxi / China. Duration: 2019 -2022.

form the third spatial dimension. Most, but not all, of the underlying arrays have the index order (`nproma`, `nlev`, `nblocks`), possibly with additional dimensions of limited size. But often the parameterization of the loop over all blocks (`nblocks`) is many subroutine levels above the loops over the block and the levels (`nproma`, `nlev`). Therefore, parallelization only over the two inner dimensions, `nproma` and `nlev` has been chosen. With this approach the optimal `nproma` is chosen as large as possible, ideally such that all cell grid points of a computational domain including first and second level halo points fit into a single block thus yielding `nblocks=1` and hence a single iteration of the `nproma` suffice. But using large block sizes, however, means also that more memory is required to store the local arrays, which can be a challenge in case of small GPU memory capacity.

- limited GPU memory:

Compared to CPU nodes, GPU nodes often have a smaller memory. Especially for the PitzDaint XC50 nodes, each equipped with a NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU, only 16 GB are available (Piz). To limit the allocation of ICON data structure, which contains field data as well as its indexing arrays¹³ OpenACC's selective deep copy was used. In addition, temporary scalar variables instead of `nproma`-sized arrays were used if possible.

- radiation model RTE+RRTMGP:

In ICON-A, the external toolbox RTE+RRTMGP (Pincus et al., 2019) is used to compute the energy transfer due to radiation. In addition to the three dimensions of ICON, radiation models contain an extra spectral dimension. To reduce this extra memory and fit it to the GPU device, a sub-blocking parameter was introduced, so that the original blocks of size `nproma` are broken up into smaller data blocks for input and output of the radiation scheme. To enable RTE+RRTMGP to make use of GPUs additional kernels using OpenACC directives were implemented and part of their higher level classes has been revised. This work was done in cooperation with the developers of this toolbox. As ICON uses a Fortran version of RTE+RRTMGP, it can not benefit from the optimisations gained in one of the ESiWACE2 Software Support Services (see D3.2 (Raffin et al., 2022)). But within the Warm World project, implementation of an improved C++ version will be investigated for ICON.

- land model JSBACH:

Instead of refactoring large parts of JSBACH, the CLAW source-to-source translator has been used for the GPU port (Clement et al., 2018). CLAW consists of a domain-specific language (DSL) and a compiler allowing it to automate the port to OpenACC. A detailed description of this work is given by Clement et al. (2019). Unfortunately, this DSL will no longer be maintained and other solutions have to be found for JSBACH.

- Validation:

A central problem of validating the ported GPU code are the slightly different results due to rounding errors. For climate and weather codes, the chaotic nature of the underlying problem further complicates the validation. These initially very small changes, which are on the order of floating point precision, quickly grow across model components and timesteps which makes distinguishing implementation bugs from chaotically grown round-off differences a non-trivial task. To handle this problem, three different test methods were used. In the "p-test" method, the model runs sequential as well as in parallel mode and calculated arrays are compared at specific synchronization points. In the "serialization" method, the model is run on CPUs as well as on GPUs. For each model component, all input- and output fields are stored. Afterwards the test binary (eg. using GPUs) reads the input used by the reference binary and compares the resulting output data with the reference data. While both methods have been used frequently to detect bugs during the porting, they do not guarantee the correctness of the overall model

¹³ICON uses an unstructured grid formulation, meaning that accesses to cell, edge and vertex neighbors go through indexing arrays.

output of a whole experiment as a small perturbation quickly accumulates across all model components and simulation timesteps. For this purpose a “tolerance testing” has been applied. It uses an ensemble of solutions, which diverge due to tiny perturbations in the initial state. Two ensembles are generated by running on CPUs and on GPUs. For validation of the GPU code, their results are compared by using a single tolerance value for each variable and timestep, resulting from statistics on the reference ensemble results. Overall, these validations are very time consuming.

In the frame of CLICCS, DKRZ is porting ICON-O to GPUs by using OpenACC directives. At the current state, the whole tracer advection as well as the ocean biochemistry model HAMOCC (HAMBURG Ocean Carbon Cycle) has been ported. While the first one is one major part of the ocean model, as it transports temperature and salinity, the second part can also be very compute intensive. In consultation with the Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie, DKRZ is further porting of ICON-O parts to GPUs as driven by necessities of the scientific experiments in focus.

For result validation of the ported function, the compiler flag `nofma` was used to suppress fused multiply-add (FMA) instructions by the NVIDIA compiler `nvhpc`. This new feature allows bit-identical comparison of the results and therefore simplifies the validation. By now, only parts of ICON-O are able to run on GPUs. These parts contain data transfer between CPU and GPU at the beginning and at the end of the respective code areas. For the overall experiment, the transfer slows down the overall performance although the ported routines show a speed up of up to nine¹⁴. Porting further ICON-O parts will reduce this bottleneck and the current data layout will be checked and might be partially reworked. Enabling ICON-O to run on GPUs would allow a coupled experiment on the LUMI-G partition, which is currently one of the most powerful supercomputer (in terms of FLOPS) in Europe.

With the reduction of compute time by using GPUs, an efficient output process becomes more and more important. Therefore, in the frame of the MONSOON-2.0 project, a so called “balanced mode” has been developed for the parallel output method CDI-PIO. In the typically used “last mode” I/O dedicated nodes are append to the list of compute nodes. As in CDI-PIO the I/O servers are running on CPUs, the GPUs of these dedicated I/O nodes are idle when the model is running on a GPU machine. In the newly developed “balanced mode” the I/O servers are distributed among the CPUs, which hosts the GPUs, allocated for computing the simulation. This reduces the time of communication, as the data does not needs to be send across nodes, and avoids unused GPU resources. In a coupled ICON test simulation, with a global horizontal resolution of 10 km, running on 77 JUWELS Booster GPU nodes, an improvement of about 15% better resource utilisation has been archived.

Main developments for using CPU machines

For the ocean part of ICON, the parallel asynchronous input/output was included. By using dedicated I/O processes, the simulations can be further integrated in time while dedicated CPUs handle the I/O. Moreover reading and writing files in parallel greatly reduces the time spent on I/O. This increased the overall performance of ICON-O, eg. shown by Hohenegger et al. (2022). Here, a coupled ICON simulation with a global horizontal resolution of 5 km, running on 420 nodes gained a 5.6× increase in SDPD. While a factor of 4 were gained by changing from the old machine Mistral to the new machine Levante, the rest is attributed to a more economic use of resources due to the introduction of asynchronous ocean output.

In ICON, a Fortran version of the radiation model RTE+RRTMGP is used. It’s CPU version has been optimised within a cooperation of DKRZ, MPI-M and Robert Pincus, the main developer of RTE+RRTMGP. The introduced reordering of the dimensions of arrays in the `gas_optics` module gained 30% - 54% increase in performance in RTE+RRTMGP stand alone experiments with different sets of g-points. For an ICON-A QUBICC experiment measurements show a gain 4.2% on CPUs and 6.5% on GPUs. The optimisations has

¹⁴This refers to the `bgc_tracer_ab` timer in a HAMOCC experiment `hamocc.omip_r2b6_10days` using a R2B6 grid.

Figure 5: Performance of three global coupled configurations run of an DYAMOND like experiment with a grid spacing of 5 km, 2.5 km and 1.25 km. Performance number were taken from (Hohenegger et al., 2022) (5 km and 2.5 km) and from (Rev) (1.25 km).

been taken over to the main development line of RTE+RRTMGP so that also more models could make advantage out of it, like the Unified Forecast System (UFS) used by NOAA.

ICON scaling on Levante

The German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) is the main provider of computing resources for MPI-M and other climate research institutes in Germany. Its super computer Levante entered service in 2022 and now consists of a CPU partition with 2832 nodes, each with 2 AMD EPYC Milan x86 processors and a GPU partition with 60 GPU nodes, each with 4 NVIDIA A100 GPUs Lev. On November 2022 Levante was ranked 53 in the top500 list.

In the frame of nextGEMS and CLICCS, scaling tests on the new Levante machine have been performed in summer 2022 and documented by Hohenegger et al. (2022). The conducted global coupled ICON simulations used the ICON-Sapphire configuration with a horizontal resolution of 5km (R2B9), 90 vertical layers in the atmosphere and 128 vertical layers in the ocean part. The experiment is similar to the DYAMOND experiment and generated an output of about 40 TB per simulated month. Its strong scaling curve is given in blue squares in Figure 5. It indicates that ICON-Sapphire scales very well with node number and a maximum throughput of 126 simulated days per day (SDPD) was reached, which corresponds to 0.34 SYPD. Increasing the node number by a factor 6, from 100 to 600 nodes, leads to a factor 5.25 increase in SDPD. Assuming an ideal linear scaling, 1745 CPU nodes would be needed to reach a throughput of 1 SYPD. This would correspond to 62% of Levante. But the ideal scaling start breaking when more then 400 nodes are used, so considerably more CPUs are needed to achieve the 1 SYPD.

Beside resolution of 5 km horizontal grid spacing, coupled simulations with 2.5 km (R2B10) and 1.25 km (R2B11) grid spacing had been performed on Levante. The later one is a two-day forecast of the so called “Blue Marble” photograph, taken by the Apollo 17 crew in 1972 (Rev), see also front figure of this deliverable. Their throughput are given in Figure 5 in red romp and green rectangle. Both simulations demonstrate the ability of ICON to perform such global high resolution simulations, which will be useful to fill pre-exascale machines.

ICON scaling on Jewels Booster

As part of the QUBICC project, main parts of ICON-A were ported to GPUs mainly by using OpenACC

Figure 6: Simulated days per day R2B9 (20 M points) based on the "integrate" timer on Piz Daint, Juwels-Booster and Levante. The black horizontal line indicates 1 simulated year per day. The thin straight line is a linear fit in $\log(\text{nodes})$ for the Juwels-Booster simulations. The vertical markers on the 1 sim. year per day line indicate the estimated number of nodes for the integration of a full year on Juwels-Booster: 984 nodes. (Giorgetta et al., 2022, Fig. 7)

directives (see above). As given in Giorgetta et al, 2022, the conducted QUBICC experiments were global ICON-A simulations using as well the Sapphire-configuration, with a horizontal resolution of 5km (R2B9) and 190 vertical layers. This experiment ran on the GPU machine PitzDaint at CSCS, on the GPU partition Booster of the JUWELS system at Jülich Supercomputing Centre (FZJ) and on the CPU partition of Levante at DKRZ. The strong scaling of their throughputs is shown in Figure 6. On Juwels-Booster (given in red) a turnover of 133 and 212 SDPD was achieved on 128 and 256 nodes respectively. The linear extrapolation in $\log(\text{nodes})$ indicates that ca. 984 nodes could return about 1 SYPD. Thus the entire Juwels-Booster system that has 936 nodes would get close to 1 SYPD with the model setup for QUBICC experiments (Giorgetta et al., 2022).

ICON running on LUMI

The primary compute power in LUMI is found in the LUMI-G hardware partition which features GPU accelerated nodes using AMD Instinct MI250X GPUs (LUM). In the frame of the projects ESiWACE2 and WarmWorld, MPI-M and DKRZ are working on running ICON-A using the Sapphire physics package on LUMI-G. This part of the ICON framework has already shown it's good scalability on Juwels Booster, by making use of NVIDIA GPU's using OpenACC directives (see Figure 6). But LUMI-G consists of AMD GPUs and AMD normally does not support OpenACC by their native compilers.

Fortunately, an ICON-A experiment has been submitted by the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS) as a benchmark for LUMI's approval. Therefore, its vendor HPE/Cray modified the Cray compiler to support OpenACC for this benchmark. End of November 2022, this benchmark experiment, an aqua-planet experiment with a horizontal resolution of 2.5 km (R02B10) without radiation, ran successfully on 2200 GPU nodes using the ICON version 2.6.0 (released in Feb. 2020). On 23.11.22, HPE/Cray delivered this compiler to the ICON consortium for further use. The first aim is now to run a recent ICON version (2.6.5, released in July'22) with an atmosphere-only nextGEMS-like experiment on LUMI-G with a horizontal resolution of 10 km (R02B08), including the radiation package RTE-RRTMGP and the land module JSBACH. Now, the work in progress is to bugfix the current ICON code with this compiler, which contains much more OpenACC

directives than the version used for the LUMI benchmark. As the most recent version of the Cray compiler is not yet installed a container is used to run ICON with the delivered Cray compiler. This approach has the disadvantages in a complicated setup of the container and a non-trivial debugging of the code within the container. As HPE/Cray just recently continued their FORTRAN support, the delivered compiler does not entirely cover all language features ICON is using in version 2.6.5. In a very close cooperation between HPE/Cray, CSC, DKRZ and MPI-M debugging of ICON is ongoing as part of the WarmWorld project. This ongoing work strongly depends on the support of HPE/Cray and therefore on their accessibility and list of priority. In addition, the ICON team suffered from the several down-time of LUMI. By the end of May 2023, porting the whole model is still work in progress and the following intermediate steps has been reached¹⁵:

- run a reduced model setup, called *Hadley test*, with a R02B9 grid (5km horizontal resolution), but the performance is worse than on Levantes A100 GPUs
- run a R02B9 aqua-planet experiment on 200 GPU nodes, but it does not scale.

Another task which is tackled is to run a coupled experiment as a heterogeneous job (het job) on LUMI-G and LUMI-C. Especially since it is not yet possible to run ICON-O entirely on GPUs, only a het job allows coupled runs. But also using CPUs for writing output files might be a possible solution for an efficient simulation. At the moment, a first test using the CPUs at LUMI-C and LUMI-G had been successful. This test is based on previous work on Levante and Jewels, where het jobs were tried to set up as well.

As a baseline to judge further developments in ICON, scaling runs of coupled simulations on LUMI-C with a horizontal resolution of 10km (R02B8) are planned in the scope of the DestinE project. Currently this is work in progress, as simulations hang when reading input data. By today, only a run with 158 km resolution (R2B4) finished successfully.

Conclusion

By comparing the throughput gained on JUWELS Booster (with GPU) and on Levante (with CPU), it could be shown, the performance increase is closer to a factor of eight, see table 3 in Giorgetta et al. (2022). This would mean that 1 SYPD would be feasible for a DYAMOND experiment performed with a coupled ICON simulation, with grid spacing of 2.5 km (R2B10) by using 1368 JUWELS GPU nodes (about 1.5 times the size of Booster) or by consuming 68 petaFLOPS. A pre-exascale machine like LUMI could provide this need, as it consists of almost twice as many GPUs as JUWELS Booster and provides 150 petaFLOPS.

4.1.4 IPSL's model IPSL-CM

The IPSL Earth System Model (IPSL-CM), in its ocean-atmosphere version, is composed of the LMDZ (atmosphere model) and NEMO (ocean models including sea ice and marine biogeochemistry) components. This coupled model allows to perform a range of climate simulations: assembled or autonomous components, coarse or fine scales, simulations from a few months to several centuries. The latest version of the model (IPSL-CM7) includes the new atmospheric dynamical core on icosahedral grid named DYNAMICO. This new version should allow targeting higher spatial resolutions than the current version, thus offering the possibility to better represent "small scale" processes. This version, in the framework of this work package, has been the subject of a computational performance evaluation in both atmosphere-only and coupled ocean-atmosphere configurations. The computing machines used for these tests are the TGCC (Très Grand Centre de Calcul du CEA) supercomputer with Irene-SKL Intel Skylake CPU comprising 1,656 nodes, 80,000 cores and 6.86 petaFLOPS, and the IDRIS JeanZay supercomputer with Intel Cascade Lake CPUs comprising of 1,528 nodes and 61 000 cores. Some tests were also performed on the IDRIS NVIDIA V100 GPU. The protocol used to collect the computation times is based on the timers available in the XIOS IOs library which is used by the model to manage its reads-writes. The parallelization of the atmospheric component DYNAMICO-LMDZ is

¹⁵For completeness we added some intermediate steps which have been reached after the date of delivery in this revision of the document.

Figure 7: Strong scalability of DYNAMICO-LMDZ (MPI-OpenMP parallelization) at resolutions 50 km (red), 25 km (green) and 12 km (blue) on Intel Skylake CPUs.

based on a hybrid MPI/OpenMP implementation while the parallelization of the oceanic component NEMO is MPI only.

Configuration DYNAMICO-LMDZ (atmosphere-only)

Irene CPU A series of preliminary tests have been performed at horizontal resolutions of 50 km and 25 km (79 vertical levels). These first tests have highlighted the impact of the aerosol part on the performance of the model, both during the initialization phase of the physical part of the model (which completely breaks the scalability of the model) but also by adding a computational overhead of about 15-20% excluding initialization. We note that an optimization work of this part will be essential and we continue our tests by deactivating it. The tests carried out then at the 12 km horizontal resolution (79 vertical levels) highlight that, at this resolution, the physical part of the model is less expensive than the dynamic part: this was expected given the reduction of the dynamic time step to 28s, compared to the 15 min time step of the physics. The times obtained at different resolutions for the DYNAMICO-LMDZ model (physics + dynamics) are shown in Figure 7. Currently, we reach about 1 SYPD at 12 km resolution on 15,360 cores (the speed-up then slows down when using more than 15,000 cores, but continues to increase, so the SYPD continues to increase too), 8 SYPD for 25 km resolution and 33 SYPD for 50 km resolution. Note that the number of computational cores referred to here represents on the model side the number of MPI processes used multiplied by the number of OpenMP threads per MPI process (here 4 OpenMP threads).

In order to investigate the strong scalability drop of the dynamic part at 12 km resolution beyond 15,000 cores, we performed weak scalability tests in hybrid MPI-OpenMP parallelization (4 threads OpenMP). For a given weak scalability curve, the local domain size, i.e. the number of cells treated by each computing core, remains constant, as the global domain size is increasing linearly with the number of cores used. Several tests have been done for different local domain sizes. Figure 8 shows the results of these tests by specifying the percentage increase between two consecutive points on the curve. We observe a good scalability for a local domain size of 40x40x79 cells up to 2560 cores and local domain size of 40x20x79 cells up to 1280 cores. But we especially notice that the scalability collapses when we increase the local domain size and the number of cores. We investigated this by disabling OpenMP parallelization and run in MPI only mode. We note that in this configuration, the model regains a good weak scalability, as can be seen in Figure 9. The first "very

fast" points corresponding to 40x40 and 40x20 domain sizes can be explained by the fact that the compute node is not completely full and that more memory bandwidth per core is therefore available.

Figure 8: Weak scalability of the dynamical core in MPI-OpenMP parallelization on Intel Skylake CPUs for local domain sizes of 40x40x79 (black), 40x20x79 (red), 20x20x79 (blue), 20x10x79 (green) and 10x10x79 (turquoise) cells.

Figure 9: Weak scalability of the dynamical core in MPI parallelization on Intel Skylake CPUs for local domain sizes of 40x40x79 (black), 40x20x79 (red), 20x20x79 (blue), 20x10x79 (green) and 10x10x79 (turquoise) cells.

These results highlight a concern related to OpenMP parallelization that would prevent us from achieving better performance. Porting to another computer would help to identify whether performance limitations are caused by the machine (beyond a certain number of cores) or the model (intrinsic problem of model parallelization).

JeanZay CPU and GPU As seen previously, we would like to put the results obtained on Intel Skylake CPU in perspective with results obtained on other computing machines. Figure 10 reports on tests performed

Figure 10: Strong scalability of the dynamical core at 12 km horizontal resolution on CPU Intel Cascade Lake (red) and GPU NVIDIA v100 (blue).

on Intel Cascade Lake CPUs and NVIDIA V100 GPUs at the beginning of the ESiWACE2 project. For the CPU part, we observe a rather constant scalability of the dynamics at 12 km up to 50,000 cores. We can see that the performance is better on Intel Cascade Lake (almost a factor of 2 in restitution time): part of this observed gain is certainly due to the better performance of the Cascade Lake processor (better memory bandwidth because fewer cores per node and more memory per node, 40 cores with 192 GB per node for Intel Cascade Lake and 48 cores with 180 GB per node for Intel Skylake). In the following, we will investigate why we do not find at all the changes observed on the Intel Skylake machine, particularly the decrease in scalability from 15,000 cores. The dynamics was also tested on the NVIDIA V100 GPU partition after optimizing the code for GPUs by integrating OpenACC directives. We can see in Figure 10 that it takes about 100 CPU cores to obtain performances equivalent to 1 GPU. We can see that CPUs scale well up to about 50,000 cores, but the performances obtained with this number of cores can be obtained more easily with GPUs, 50,000 cores being more difficult to obtain than 500 GPUs.

Configuration ocean-atmosphere DYNAMICO-LMDZ coupled to NEMO4

The coupled ocean-atmosphere configuration of the IPSL is composed of DYNAMICO-LMDZ for the atmosphere part and NEMO for the ocean part. The tests carried out in this study were performed using the NEMO 4.0.7 version of the ocean model on the Intel Skylake CPU machine of the TGCC. Starting from a coupled configuration using NEMO 3.6, the first step of this work was to implement version 4 of the NEMO ocean model. The OASIS-MCT coupler is used to exchange and interpolate the fields between the atmospheric and oceanic components. The LUCIA performance measurement tool, available with OASIS coupler, will be used here to measure the computation times of each component of the coupled system. Figure 11 represents the IPSL-CM model times at different horizontal atmospheric and oceanic resolutions ranging from 200 km to 25 km. The scalability curves of the coupled system show that at low resolution (200 km atmosphere and 200 km ocean) the scalability is good up to 2560 cores, with 66 years simulated per day and that at high resolution (25 km atmosphere and 25 km ocean) we simulate 6.8 years per day on 12 800 cores. We find here the same characteristics as in the atmosphere-only configuration, i.e. that the scalability decreases beyond 12 000 cores at 25 km resolution, but the SYPD continues to increase. A coupled ocean-atmosphere configuration at 12 km horizontal resolution could not be set up because we focused on the performance of

Figure 11: Strong scalability in SYPD of DYNAMICO-LMDZ-NEMO4 model on machine CPU Intel Skylake with horizontal atmospheric and oceanic resolutions of: DYNAMICO-LMDZ 200km NEMO4 200km (red), DYNAMICO-LMDZ 200km NEMO4 25km (blue) and DYNAMICO-LMDZ 25km NEMO4 25km (green).

the atmosphere-only DYNAMICO-LMDZ model at this resolution. Finally, one of the next steps will be to use the NEMO 4.2 version (instead of 4.0.7 version) benefiting from the last optimizations that have been made, in order to target the future computing architectures.

Conclusion

This study allowed us to evaluate the performance of the DYNAMICO-LMDZ model at different resolutions both in atmosphere-only and in coupled ocean-atmosphere configuration with NEMO4 on different CPU and GPU based computers. We found several bottlenecks that need to be investigated: the activation of the aerosol component has a strong impact on the computational performance as the resolution increases, the dynamic part seems to scale differently on different machines when increasing the number of cores and the resolution, in particular when using the hybrid MPI-OpenMP parallelization. The XIOS timers used did not allow an in-depth investigation to find the scalability problems encountered on the Intel Skylake machines and it will therefore be necessary to use profiling tools for a more thorough study. The I/O part has not been evaluated here and the tests have been performed on configurations with very light I/O or without I/O. But an evaluation work on the latest version of the XIOS tool (used in the IPSL model to manage I/Os) is currently underway elsewhere, with a particular focus on the memory footprint and computational performance of NEMO4 high-resolution configuration, both for reading and writing data.

A first porting on accelerated machines, in particular GPUs, was realised for the dynamical core. Work on adapting the physics part of LMDZ to GPUs started in 2021 at IPSL and is still in progress. Finally, in addition to the information on the computational performance of the model that has been obtained, the intermediate configurations that have been implemented will all be candidates for the future model and as such the subject of a scientific evaluation. Currently, we are validating the low resolution version at 200 km in order to use it

soon in production.

4.1.5 The NEMO model

A new very-high resolution global configuration ($1/36^\circ$, 2 to 3 kilometres) has been developed and implemented in NEMO OGCM¹⁶; it is hereafter called ORCA36. It is targeting the future CMEMS operational forecast system and is based on the NEMO 4.2 OGCM.

Model configuration

ORCA36 uses the quasi-isotropic ORCA grid (Madec and Imbard, 1996) and has about 12000×10000 points in the horizontal direction. Vertical discretization uses 75 z levels with partial cell parameterization Barnier et al. (2006) which leads to a resolution ranging from 1 m at the surface to 450 m at depth.

The bathymetry is based on the GEBCO_2019 Grid (GEBCO, 2019) to build the global ocean bathymetry and Bedmachine Antarctica 2 (Morlighem et al., 2019) has been used to build the Antarctic cavities bathymetry and ice caps geometry. GSHHG (Wessel and Smith, 1996) data are used to build the coastline.

The atmosphere used to force the ocean model is the ECMWF/IFS real time system. Previous ORCA36 hindcasts were forced with IFS at 14 km resolution and 3 hours frequency. Here the new version of IFS has been used to force our configuration, with a resolution of 9 km and a 1-hour frequency.

For the initial conditions, we used the WOA13 climatology (Locarnini et al. (2013)) for temperature and salinity and sea-ice parameters are extracted from the CMEMS/Mercator $1/4^\circ$ reanalysis GLORYS2V4.

Numerical setup

The present global $1/36^\circ$ configuration uses a non-linear free surface (z^* coordinates system) associated to the Quasi-Eulerian Coordinates.

Tracers' transport is computed with a 4th order FCT advection scheme on horizontal and vertical and an explicit diffusion with iso-neutral operator. The equation of state is based on EOS80. Momentum is computed with a 3rd order UBS advection scheme and there is no explicit viscosity. Vorticity is computed with an energy and enstrophy scheme. The hydrostatic pressure gradient is computed with a s-coordinate standard Jacobian formulation. For vertical physics, we used the GLS scheme and an adaptive-implicit vertical advection (Shchepetkin, 2015). For the boundary conditions, we used partial slip for the lateral friction and a logarithmic top (under ice cavities) bottom drag coefficient.

Surface fluxes are computed with the ECMWF bulk formulation. Atmospheric pressure gradient is added in ocean and ice equations. A 3 bands scheme (RGB scheme) is used for light penetration. For the tidal forcing, we used the tidal potential, with 5 components: O1, K1, M2, S2 and N2 and a self attraction and loading term coming from FES2014 tidal atlas (see Madec, 2019, section 6.8).

The Sea Ice model is the SI3 model shipped with NEMO, with 5 categories and levitating sea ice.

Multiyear hindcasts

Multi-year hindcasts have been produced in 2022. Figure 12 describes the hindcasts setup. These hindcasts have been produced on the new ECMWF Atos Bullsequana XH2000 computer.

It consists of 3 years spin up without tidal forcing, followed by two twin 3-years long experiments, one without tidal forcing and one with tidal forcing. The same setup has been realized with the 2 coarser resolution configurations, ORCA025 (18-20 km resolution) and ORCA12 (6-9 km resolution), to quantify the impact of the increase of horizontal resolution. Based on this portfolio of experiment, it is possible to assess of the impact of tidal forcing on the circulation and the impact of resolution on the tidal solution. The last year of all the hindcasts will be produced with 3D-hourly model outputs, to study high frequency motions.

¹⁶NEMO OGCM web-page: <https://www.nemo-ocean.eu/>

Figure 12: NEMO hindcast set up.

Computing performances tests

Different developments implemented in NEMO have been tested with ORCA36 configuration, to measure their improvements on the computing performances. Scalability tests have been performed on the new ECMWF/ATOS computer. 10 000 to 40 000 cores have been used. Each test has been performed over a 1-day simulation.

Impact of tiling on performances

A first development consists in improving NEMO OGCM to fully exploit memory hierarchies and hardware peak performance: each local MPI domain is splitted in sub-domains called ‘tiles’ so that computations deal with smaller arrays, which prefers the use of fast cache memory access. Tiling has been applied to 7 routines in NEMO. Tiling implementation was possible only with 2 cells MPI halos (in standard, MPI halos has a size of 1 cell): it is called “wider haloes”.

Figure 13 shows the performances for 3 routines and Figure 14 for the total over the 7 routines. For each routine, we compare the performance for a case without wider halos and without tiling, a case with wider haloes and a case with wider haloes and tiling, with tiles size from 5 to 40 grid points. Wider halos gives a light improvement for all MPI processes number tested.

Behavior of tiling is not the same for all routines. Tiling with little tile sizes (5,10) improves the performance regardless of core numbers. Figure 14 shows the performances for the 7 routines impacted by tiling. It can be concluded that the size should be carefully tuned and using little sizes (5,10) leads to a 10 to 20% gain. Currently an effort to apply tiling to more routines in NEMO is still in progress.

Figure 13: Elapsed time for 3 different routines: case without wider haloes and without tiling (grey), case with wider haloes and without tiling (black) and case with wider haloes and tiling, with tiles size from 5 to 40 (yellow to purple).

Figure 14: Total elapsed time (left) and gain (right) for the 7 routines impacted by: case without wider haloes and without tiling (grey), case with wider haloes and without tiling (black) and case with wider haloes and tiling, with tiles size from 5 to 40 (yellow to purple).

Impact of tiling of DO-loop fusion on performances

“Loop fusion” was intended to maximize the level of vectorization. Loop Fusion has been applied in 3 routines in NEMO: `tra1df` for the active tracers’ lateral diffusion, `traadv` for the active tracers’ advection and `dynvor` for the vorticity terms.

As for tiling, Do-loop fusion was possible only with 2 cells MPI halos (in standard, MPI halos has a size of 1 cell): it is called “wider haloes”. Figure 15 shows the scalability tests for each routine. For `traadv` and `dynvor` routines, wider haloes and loop fusion improve the performances, not in `tra1df`. Figure 16 shows the total time to solution for the 3 routines and the gain. Wider haloes and loop fusion induce together a gain of 5% for 3840 cores; this gain decreases to zero when the core number increases to 40,000.

Figure 15: Elapsed time for 3 different routines: case without wider haloes (black), case with wider haloes (red) and case with wider haloes and loop fusion (blue).

Impact of reducing MPI communications

A reduction of the number of MPI communications has been realized between NEMO 4.0 and 4.2 releases. Figure 17 shows the scalability tests for the 2 releases. The run with 40 000 cores and NEMO 4.0 crashed for an Out of Memory. In term of simulated year per days (SYPD), using NEMO 4.2 leads to a gain of performances from 10% to 25% with ORCA36 configuration. It can produce a 0.3 to 0.9 million CPU hour gain for a 1-year run. An additional test has consisted in replacing the z^* vertical coordinate formulation Vertical Varying Layer (VVL) to QCO (stands for Quasi-Eulerian Coordinates), only over 1 MPI splitting. It

Figure 16: Timing of the total solution (left) and gain (right), for the 3 routines impacted by: case without wider haloes (black), case with wider haloes (red) and case with wider haloes and loop fusion (blue).

Figure 17: Scalability test with NEMO 4.0.7 (black) and NEMO 4.2 (red). Left: Simulated Year per Days, Right: gain.

induces a reduction of 7,5% elapsed time reduction.

Impact of RK3 time-stepping scheme

A new numerical time-stepping scheme has been introduced in NEMO. It is a 2-level scheme based on a third order Runge Kutta (RK3) and it will replace the present Modified Leap Frog (MLF). This new numerical scheme is more stable and authorize to increase the time-step value and then, to decrease the CPU cost.

Figure 18 shows the elapsed time for a 5-days run performed with the MLF scheme and the RK3 scheme. With the same time-step value, RK3 scheme is more expensive. But, thanks to its stability, time-step value has been multiplied by 2.5 and the elapsed time has been decrease of 30%.

Conclusion

Different developments have been tested on the ORCA36 configuration to see how they can improve its computing performances.

Reducing the MPI communications leads to an improvement of 10 to 25%. Changing the non-linear free surface (z^*) formulation leads to a reduction of 7,5% elapsed time. Loop fusion induces a gain of elapsed

Figure 18: Left: Elapsed time for a 5-days run for a run with Modified Leap-Frog scheme (MLF, black) and the 2-level scheme (RK3, red) with different time-step values. Right: gain with the 2-level scheme (RK3) with different time-step values compared to the Leap-Frog scheme (MLF).

time of 5% for low core number on routines where it has been implemented. Using little tiles sizes (5,10) leads to a 10 to 20 % gain of elapsed time on routines where it has been implemented. Thanks to its better numerical stability, the new RK3 time-stepping scheme authorizes to increase the time-step of the model and by consequence obtain a gain of 30% of elapsed time.

Multiyear hindcasts (covering 3 years) has been produced with the ORCA36 (2-3 km resolution) configuration and the coarser resolutions configurations ORCA12 (6-9 km resolution) and ORCA025 (18-20 km resolution). 3D hourly model outputs are available for a one-year period.

During the last years, the NEMO based ORCA36 configuration computing performances has been improved and its numerical performances has been also improved thanks to the new physics introduced.

4.2 Testing Ensemble Analysis in practice

A late change to the project involved replacing a planned investment by the Met Office in testing a managed ensemble at scale on a pre-exascale machine, with a science test of a similar ensemble on the ARCHER2 (very large CPU) system in the UK being carried out by NCAS-UREAD.

High resolution is not the only way we expect to exploit large machines. Ensembles will also be important for scientific studies and policy advise, as they provide an estimate for forecast uncertainties, and they bring data handling problems. One way of mitigating this data handling problems is to avoid writing the data to disk and do the analysis *in-situ*. Hence, the major objective of the ensemble analysis work is to investigate using a large fraction of a big machine to carry a single ensemble, and in doing so, carry out some ensemble analysis without the data ever hitting disk. The long-term goal is to enable large ensembles where some or all ensemble members only contribute to ensemble statistics of some variables (i.e. the individual ensemble member data is not written to disk).

Much of the work in setting up the ensemble analysis system was carried out in WP4. In WP1, the objective was to find a suitable science problem, find a suitable ensemble configuration, and set up an ensemble analysis system for production use in that science problem.

There are two considerations: the ensemble scaling, and the science being done with the ensemble. Here we introduce the latter, and describe the ensemble configuration used, and put it in the context of ensemble

scaling results. The WP1 contribution to this work has been to develop the science case and test and set up the ensemble suite. The actual science runs, results and analysis appear elsewhere as they continue far beyond the end of the project.

4.2.1 Scientific Problem

One tends to use an ensemble to investigate variability, either internal to the climate system, or in the forcing. We have chosen to investigate the latter here.

We know that variations in sea surface temperature (SST) have a profound influence on key processes in the atmosphere elsewhere. For example, the SST in the North Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea affects wind and precipitation in both Europe and West Africa. To that end we have constructed an experiment that utilises an ensemble of SST states which we use to force an ensemble of atmospheric model simulations. The resulting ensemble will be analysed to understand how future changes in SST forcing might impact those regions so as to give better information to decisions makers.

Our initial interest is to investigate how precipitation might change due to climate change. We know that changes in precipitation have strong societal impact. For example, in the Sahel around 65% of the labour force and 95% of the land use are devoted to rain-fed agriculture, and one third of the gross domestic product depends on the agricultural sector. We also know from previous work that such changes in precipitation are tied to uncertainty at simulating future changes in temperature over the North Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea, but the detailed influence of these changes are currently unquantified.

To address this we have constructed a ten member set of SSTs which span some of the known possible future SST changes. (They are chosen from simulations carried out as part of the sixth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, CMIP6). We are using those to force a centennial duration ten member set of global atmosphere models (the particular model we are using is the full physics version of the GA7 version of the UK Unified Model – UM – running at N216, or about 60 km horizontal resolution).

4.2.2 Technical Configuration

Each member is running the UM at N216 resolution - this was the default high resolution physical model configuration used by the Met Office during CMIP6. A higher resolution model configuration could have been used (we have tested similar sized ensembles at N512, or about 25km, but being a much slower and more expensive model, this would have been unaffordable for the duration and resources available).

Each model component is running with 32x28 MPI tasks and 2 OMP threads which requires 14 ARCHER2 nodes (1792 cores). The XIOS (V2.5 rev 2245) configuration supporting the ensemble analysis and output utilises 8 nodes with 2 servers running per node, and so the entire ensemble is running on 148 nodes (or just under 19000 cores). This configuration of the model runs standalone at approximately 2.6 simulated years per day (SYPD), we could run faster as the UM is still scaling at this resolution at 14 nodes, but at an unacceptable throughput cost for this experiment.

As can be seen from our ensemble scaling (figure 19) we could have run a much larger ensemble, but for production this size was chosen in attempt to optimise how much variability we could span, how much could be afforded within a limited ARCHER2 budget, and how quickly we could get through the machine (actual simulated years per day depend on queue waiting time etc).

The ensemble duration is 100 years, so this is effectively a thousand years of simulation running in ten parallel streams. We expect the ensemble to run at 2 SYPD, so the ensemble expense will be approximately 1800 node hours per simulated year (NHSY), or 178 thousand node hours. The minimum time to complete the experiment will be 50 days, but in practice we expect it to take much longer, allowing for queuing time etc.

For this first real ensemble science test, the ensemble diagnostics will initially only include obvious statistical operators such as the standard deviation operator (the XML for the XIOS standard deviation ensemble operator is shown in D4.3 (Lawrence et al., 2023)).

Figure 19: Ensemble scaling for the UM atmosphere only at N216 resolution. Note the considerable amount of jitter on ARCHER2 (nodes are 128 core AMD Rome). Note that the performance of ensemble diagnostics (i.e the overhead per extra core member, which is here 3.4%) is expected to be much better in later versions of XIOS.

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6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

As discussed earlier in the deliverable, we haven't had access to the pre-exascale EuroHPC machines in time, to be able to perform meaningful strong scalability tests to enable us to extrapolate compute performance to the exascale within this deliverable. However, we have progressed the developments of the individual models on multi-peta-scale machines and the new hardware configurations that will be available once the pre-exascale machines become ready.

Please also note that the work on the ensemble I/O – which is documented in this Deliverable in section 4.2 – has been delayed from Deliverable D1.1 due to a change in responsibility and the transaction of corresponding person months between the UK MetOffice and NCAS.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

This deliverable is an important contribution towards the European strategy for HPC as it develops large HPC applications which can leverage the power of European pre-exascale and exascale machines when they become available. Furthermore, the applications have a direct pathway to impact as the model configurations that are optimised in EsiWACE2 WP1 can straightaway be used by large EU projects that use the tools to understand more about weather and climate (e.g. nextGEMS and WarmWorld) and also towards operational weather and climate predictions as realised at ECMWF or in the DestinE project. The tests and the comparison between the different models generates synergies between the modelling centres and helps to identify challenges and bottlenecks for the operational use of these computing resources.

8 Sustainability

The production mode simulations of ESiWACE will feed directly into the development of the Digital Twins of the Earth as part of the DestinE project which are based on operational, global, coupled simulations at unprecedented resolution for both weather and climate. This includes the configuration of both of the twins that are already worked on, namely the extremes twin which is looking into weather-type simulations very similar to those performed with IFS and ICON in the above, and the climate twin which based on model configurations that are very similar to those from EC-Earth as described above. The IFS and ICON configurations above are also very similar to the model configuration that are used in the nextGEMS project (30-year-long integration with IFS and ICON at storm-resolving resolution), and future simulations in the WarmWorld project in Germany. The performance improvements that were realised in the work for this deliverable will therefore lead to direct improvements for scientific projects and studies in Europe. Furthermore, the model configurations of ICON and IFS are exploited for the simulations in the DYAMOND model intercomparison project, which is also supported by Work Package 1 of ESiWACE2.

The simulations with the IFS model of this deliverable directly inform the future plans for operational weather predictions at ECMWF and improvements in model efficiency and scalability will benefit all ECMWF Member and Co-operating States or users of ECMWF weather predictions. The EC-Earth model will be used for climate model simulations and are in preparation for the next Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and improvements in scalability and performance will benefit the entire EC-Earth community.

NEMO is used as an ocean-only model but also as an ocean component of a number of coupled model configurations (including the DYNAMICO, IFS and EC-Earth). The possibility to run high-resolution 1/36° simulations with the NEMO model will therefore benefit a number of modelling groups and applications in both weather and climate prediction.

ICON is used as the production model of the German Weather service, and in a multitude of international weather and climate research projects. Improvements to the model will directly benefit the weather forecasts of the national weather services participating in the COSMO consortium (Germany, Switzerland, Italy, Greece, Poland, Romania, Russia, Israel), as well as a rich scientific research community.

While the production model simulations are directly benefiting from the developments in Work Package 2 – in particular regarding the developments of domain specific languages and concurrent integrations of model components – the production runs of Work Package 1 will serve as reference for the Earth System MiddleWare (ESDM) of Work Package 4 and the visualisation of Work Package 5. For the latter, in particular the simulations of the DYAMOND model intercomparison are important.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We ensure the uptake of the deliverable by the targeted audience through the following actions

The models that are improved in this workpackage are leading weather and climate model configurations that are not only used for operational weather predictions (for example at ECMWF and DWD) and climate predictions (for example for CMIP simulations). The models are also used by a number of follow on projects to improve our scientific understanding of the model simulations, predictability and the Earth system as such, including nextGEMS, WarmWorld, EERIE and DestinE. There will also be continued support for ICON, IFS and NEMO in the ESiWACE3 follow-on project that has started 1st January 2023.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See Table 1.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

See Table 2.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A

Table 1: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Meeting presentation	ARMing the IFS: Experiments and experiences from porting the ECMWF model to Fugaku	May 9 2022, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6805913	80
Conference poster	ARM-Powered Numerical Weather Prediction: Running the ECMWF Model on Fugaku	27 June 2022, PASC, Basel	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6806031	200
Conference presentation	Toward a community global 1/36° ORCA36 configuration based on NEMO 4	01/10/2021 online, CLIVAR/Ocean Model Development Panel, Future Directions in Basin and Global	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5571815	200

Table 2: Publications related to this deliverable

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Published	More accuracy with less precision	Lang, Dawson, Diamantakis, Dueben, et al.	QJRMS	Open access
Published	Fluid Simulations Accelerated With 16 Bits: Approaching 4x Speedup on A64FX by Squeezing ShallowWaters.jl Into Float16	Kloewer, Hatfield, Croci, Dueben, Palmer	JAMES	Open access
Published	A baseline for global weather and climate simulations at 1 km resolution	Wedi, Polichtchouk, Dueben, et al.	JAMES	Open access
Published	Compressing atmospheric data into its real information content	Kloewer, Dominguez, Dueben, Palmer, Razinger,	Nature Computational Science	Open access
In preparation	Single-precision ocean modeling at ECMWF	Hatfield, Mogensen, Roberts, Keeley, Johnson, Senan, Düben	TBD	Open access
Published	Building Tangent-Linear and Adjoint Models for Data Assimilation With Neural Networks	Hatfield, Chantry, Dueben, Lopez, Geer, Palmer	JAMES	Open access
Published	Icon-sapphire: simulating the components of the earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales	Hohenegger, Korn, Linardakis, Redler, Schnur, Adamidis, et al.	Geosci. Model Dev	Open access